

Heuristic Explainability Evaluation Questionnaire

Based on: Deters et al. (2025) — Information and Software Technology

System Clarity (Explainability) — Literature-Based Quality Model

Evaluator Name		Date	
System Evaluated		Role	

Instructions: For each heuristic, mark a fit score (1–5), describe any identified issues, and indicate your confidence level (1–5).

Heuristic & Example	Issues Identified	Score (1–5)	Confidence (1–5)
1. Understandability			
#1 Language is simple and clear in the technical and contextual domain. Example: Assembly instructions and UI elements do not use complex sentence structures or advanced engineering terms that novice students would not understand.	—		—
#2 Length of explanation and virtual animation is appropriate for the required information. Example: Simple assembly steps are accompanied by a short graphical cue or a single directional arrow; complex engineering steps include a detailed 3D animation showing the exact connection angle.	—		—
#3 The virtual display does not include unnecessary graphical elements (preventing visual overload). Example: Robot parts that have already been successfully assembled are not highlighted again.	—		—
#4 The form of instruction presentation is adapted to the type of assembly task (text vs. 3D). Example: Positions and connection angles of mechanical components are presented visually and in 3D in Unity	—		—

(because they are hard to convey in text), while score indicators or step numbers appear as clean text in the UI.			
<p>#5 Instructional components and steps are presented in a coherent, consistent, and logically organized manner.</p> <p>Example: The step order maintains a logical engineering assembly sequence; terminology is consistent; the 3D guide contains no contradictions with the physical robot structure.</p>	—		—
2. Transparency			
<p>#6 The system clarifies the need for physical input requirements or camera scans.</p> <p>Example: If it is not self-evident why the application requires the user to move the camera or scan a particular texture, the system provides appropriate guidance.</p>			—
<p>#7 The system explains the consequences of different navigation actions or user choices.</p> <p>Example: Students clearly understand the difference between pressing the 'right arrow' button and stopping, and how that action will affect the star rating and score.</p>			—
<p>#8 It is completely clear which physical or virtual component the current instruction refers to.</p> <p>Example: The system highlights precisely (e.g., by changing a part's color) the exact location where the current gear or motor should be assembled, eliminating confusion about the component group.</p>			—
3. Effectiveness			
<p>#9 The AR information helps the student make decisions about the assembly.</p> <p>Example: When a component connection instruction is shown, the system accompanies it with a short visual explanation of the component's function (e.g., 'Connect the wheel to enable the robot to drive').</p>			

<p>#10 The data displayed by the system enables the user to perform meaningful correction or learning actions.</p> <p>Example: If a student struggles at a step or realizes they made an incorrect connection, the application allows full freedom to return to previous assembly sections, replay the 3D guidance animation, or change the virtual viewing angle to correct the mistake.</p>			
<h4>4. Efficiency</h4>			
<p>#11 Students can grasp and understand the assembly step and interface data at maximum speed.</p> <p>Example: Textual instructions on the phone screen use short, focused sentences. Spatial instructions in Unity use contrasting colors and immediately distinguishable graphical elements.</p>	—		—
<p>#12 The shared interface and 3D display do not contain duplicate information, buttons, or elements.</p> <p>Example: There is no duplication of navigation buttons and virtual robot parts are not displayed twice.</p>	—		—
<p>#13 Updates to graphics, detection, and placement of AR components are perceived as immediate by the learner.</p> <p>Example: The system avoids perceptible latency when loading the 3D model, and the student's progress data is updated continuously in the background of the central management system.</p>	—		—
<h4>5. Satisfaction</h4>			
<p>#14 Navigation buttons and instructions are easily accessible.</p> <p>Example: Forward/back navigation buttons are always at the same fixed, convenient position on the mobile screen; the star-display system is accessible without interrupting the work flow.</p>	—		—

<p>#15 Virtual guides do not physically or visually interfere with the assembly.</p> <p>Example: AR arrows and graphics appear at exactly the right moment, and their spatial position does not obstruct the student's ability to physically insert pins or mechanical parts.</p>	—		—
<h2>6. Suitability</h2>			
<p>#16 Short attention transition and mental effort: AR instructions can be absorbed quickly in the context in which they are presented.</p> <p>Example: The system avoids lengthy textual explanations; instructions are compact and adapted to a dynamic physical work environment.</p>			
<p>#17 Virtual elements and visual metaphors are adapted to the students' background.</p> <p>Example: Are the icons, arrows, and colors in the application intuitive and understandable?</p>			
<p>#18 The language and technological terminology are understandable given the prior knowledge of STEM learners.</p> <p>Example: Use of concepts from robotics and mechanics (e.g., 'servo motor', 'ultrasonic sensor', 'gear wheels') is appropriate and suitable for students with a basic background in the field.</p>			
<p>#19 The level of detail in explanations and guides can be adjusted or filtered to the user's level.</p> <p>Example: Advanced users or those already familiar with the build steps can reduce or hide the guiding arrows and text, leaving only the final 3D model, according to their personal pace.</p>			
<h2>7. Trustability</h2>			

<p>#20 AR components and animations are completely consistent with each other.</p> <p>Example: The robot model, step order, and learning metrics (such as star display) in the smartphone app are identical to the data shown to the instructor in the central web system; the instructions complement rather than contradict each other.</p>	—		—
<p>#21 Consistent detection accuracy: similar system behavior under similar circumstances leads to similar instruction display.</p> <p>Example: Scanning the same robot texture or reaching the same assembly step under similar lighting conditions always leads to a precise, fixed, and identical placement of virtual objects, with no random positional variation.</p>	—		—

General Summary and Overall Impression

Question	Response
Which aspects were most relevant to the system's intended explanatory purpose?	
Which experiences revealed the most significant issues?	
Were there any particularly helpful explanations? Please describe.	
Additional notes or improvement suggestions:	

Overall Clarity Rating

1 — Very Poor	2 — Poor	3 — Adequate	4 — Good	5 — Excellent
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